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SYSTEMATIC AND GEOGRAPHICAL ANALYSIS OF THE GENUS *VERBASCUM* L. (*CELSIA* L.) IN THE FLORA OF NAKHCHIVAN AUTONOMOUS REPUBLIC

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Abstract

There are more than 300 species of the *Verbascum* L. genus, which is included in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. There are 40 species in the Caucasus, 25 in Azerbaijan, and 22 in Nakhchivan MR, and 4 of them are common only in Nakhchivan: *V. cheiranthifolium* Boiss., *V. erivanicum* E.Wulf, *V. Flavidum* (Boiss.) Freyn. & Bornm., *V. formosum* Fisch. ex Schrank, *V. georgicum* Benth., *V. gossypinum* Bieb., *V. macrocarpum* Boiss., *V. nudicaule* (Wydł.) Takht., *V. oreophilum* C.Koch, *V. orientale* (L.) All., *V. paniculatum* E.Wulf, *V. phlomoides* L., *V. phoeniceum* L., *V. pyramidatum* Bieb., *V. saccatum* C.Koch, *V. songoricum* Schrenk, *V. speciosum* Schrad, *V. suworowianum* (C.Koch) O.Kuntze, *V. szovitsianum* Boiss., *V. adenosepalum* (Murb.) Karjag. 2 of them are endemic of Azerbaijan and 1 of the Caucasus. *V. erivanicum* E.Wulf, *V. Paniculatum* E.Wulf, *V. saccatum* C.Koch species are distributed only in the territory of the autonomous republic of Azerbaijan. Many species of *Verbascum* L. species are widely used as ornamental and medicinal plants.

Keywords: *Verbascum* L., systematic analysis, geographic elements, genus, species, life form

Introduction: The modern territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic occupies an important place in the Caucasus with its genesis and geographical location. The territory located on the border of several botanical-geographical regions enters the flora migration with the Caucasus, Central Asia, Front Asia and Iran. As a result of the researches, it is clear that the modern flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic is represented by 176 families, 908 genera and 3021 species of high-spored, gymnospermous and angiospermous plants, of which 1050 species are found in the plains, 1869 species in the mountainous parts, and 400 species in both plains and spread in the mountainous part. This amount is 60.38% of the flora of Azerbaijan (5000). Extensive research work is being carried out for the more detailed study and discovery of these resources, their protection and efficient use.

Although the flora of the autonomous republic is generally studied, there are separate genera and species about which there is very little or no information. Among these plants, the role of representatives of the genus *Verbascum* L. in the biodiversity of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, the distribution, the identification of the prospects for the use of its important species, and the cultivation in local conditions have not been studied in detail so far. From this point of view, comprehensive study of the species included in the genus in the territorial flora on scientific grounds, identification of useful species, protection and transmission to future generations are extremely important issues.

Material and methodology: The main material for the study was the species belonging to the genus *Verbascum* L. distributed in the mountainous and plain ar-

reas of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The following methods were used to study this vegetation. Determining ecological groups using digital cameras for research, GPS devices for accurate coordinates determination, specifiers, magnifiers and microscopes was carried out based on the methods of A.P. Shennikov, and phenological observations on plants were carried out based on the methods of I.N. Beydeman. The works of T.H.Talibov, E.M. Gurbanov, and V.S. Novruzov, among the Azerbaijani scientists, were used in the study of the species included in the genus *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.). The works of L.I. Prilipko, A.S.Ibrahimov, A.A.Grossheim, N.N.Portenier were used in the classification and geobotanical regionalization of vegetation, and in the definition of geographical elements.

Discussion of results: A.A. Grossheim came to the territory of Sadarak region in 1915 and studied the flora there, "Flora of the Caucasus" [10, p. 452-472] and in the VII volume of "Flora of Azerbaijan" published later [4, p. 415-442] made generalizations and indicated 23 species [*V. phlooides* L., *V. georgicum* Benth., *V. thapsus* L., *V. songoricum* Schr., *V. speciosum* Schrad., *V. megaphlomos* Boiss., *V. cheiranthifolium* Boiss., *V. stachydiforme* Boiss., *V. adenosepalum* Murb., *V. gossypinum* M.B., *V. varians* Fr. Et Sint., *V. laxum* Filar., *V. Szovitsianum* Boiss., *V. erivanicum* Wulff., *V. paniculatum* Wulff., *V. formosum* Fisch., *V. saccatum* C. Koch., *V. punalense* Boiss., *V. pyramidatum* M.B., *V. oreophilum* C. Koch., *V. macrocarpum* Boiss., *V. blattaria* L., *V. phoeniceum* L., *V. flavidum* Boiss.,], 4 species of *Celsia* L. genus [*C. orientalis* L., *C. nudicaulis* Wydł., *C. Suworowiana* C. Koch., *C. heterophylla* Desf.] of the genus *Verbascum* L. It was noted that 19 of these species belong to the flora of the autonomous republic.

In volume VII of the last fundamental works "Flora of the Caucasus" written by A.A. Grossheim later as a result of generalizations [10, p. 452-472] the

genus *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.) has been allocated a wide area, and the species distributed in the territory of Nakhchivan AR have been shown. In this valuable work, along with the biology of the species, their geographical area types are also mentioned. A.A.Grossheim in his work "Flora of the Caucasus" identified 40 species of the genus *Verbascum* L. and 4 species of the genus *Celsia* L. and described them, of which 17 species of *Verbascum* L. and 3 species of *Celsia* L. are distributed in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

Species belonging to the genus *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.) were studied in the flora of countries bordering the Republic of Azerbaijan. The description of 228 species of the genus was presented in the work "Flora of Turkey and the East Aegean Islands" [16, p. 470-603].

The flora of the Islamic Republic of Iran, which borders the Republic of Azerbaijan to the south, is quite rich. Since the nature of the regions of this state bordering the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are similar, we focused on the flora of Iran in our research. In the research work "Flora Iranica" it was determined that the genus *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.) is represented by 56 species, and some of these species are also found in the flora of the autonomous republic [15, p. 78- 110].

During the research conducted by T.H.Talibov and A.S.Ibrahimov, the flora biodiversity of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic was studied, the species composition of the local flora and the structure of the vegetation formed by them were determined [2, p. 12-13; 3, p. 84; 8, p. 191-192].

T.H.Talibov's research work entitled "Flora biodiversity of Nakhchivan AR, its efficient use and protection" [2, p.84] shows that there are 21 species belonging to the genus *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.). A.S.Ibrahimov's research work entitled "Vegetation of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, its productivity and botanical-geographical zoning" presented the position of the genus in the vegetation formed in the territory of the autonomous republic.

A systematic analysis of 30 species of the genus *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.) is given in A.M. Askerov's work entitled "Plants of Azerbaijan". 21 species of these [*V. agrimoniifolium* (C. Koch) Hubert Morath, *V. cheiranthifolium* Boiss., *V. erivanicum* E. Wulf, *V. flavidum* (Boiss.) Freyn et Bornm., *V. formosum* Fisch. ex Schrank, *V. georgicum* Benth., *V. gossypinum* Bieb., *V. macrocarpum* Boiss., *V. nudicaule* (Wydł.) Takht., *V. oreophilum* C. Koch, *V. orientale* (L.) All., *V. paniculatum* E. Wulf, *V. phlomoides* L., *V. phoeniceum* L., *V. pyramidatum* Bib., *V. saccatum* C. Koch, *V. sinuatum* L., *V. songaricum* Schrenk, *V. speciosum* Schrad., *V. sinuatum* L., *V. suworowianum* (C. Koch) O. Kuntze, *V. szovitsianum* Boiss.] were shown to be characteristic of the territory of the autonomous republic. For the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, one of the species (*V. erivanicum* E. Wulf,) is listed as endemic, and two (*V. paniculatum* E. Wulf, *V. szovitsianum* Boiss.) are listed as subendemic [1, p. 330-331].

Taxonomic composition of the genus and species of *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.) in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic "Flora of Azerbaijan",

"Flora of the Caucasus" [4, p. 415-442; 10, p. 452-472], "Flora of Azerbaijan" [9, p. 415-442], "Flora of the USSR", Cherepanov S.K., "Synopsis of Caucasian flora" [11, p.142-217], and later elaborated by T.H.Talibov and A.S.Ibrahimov. So T.H.Talibov, A.S. Ibrahimov's work entitled "Taxonomic spectrum of the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic (Plants with higher spores, gymnosperms and angiosperms)" shows 21 species included in the genus *Verbascum* L. [8, p. 191-192]. In 2016, as a result of the research conducted by T. Talibov, A. Ibrahimov and F. Nabiyeva in the local flora, the species *Verbascum sinuatum* L. was assigned to the genus *Verbascum* L. [7, p. 76-83; 8, p. 73-79]. Thus, it was determined that 22 species of the genus are distributed in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, that these species play a major role in the formation of the flora, and the naming and systematic composition of the species is given according to the APG III system [14, p. 105-121].

As a result of research carried out by us during expeditions to different areas of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic and based on literature data, the systematic composition of the genus *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.) distributed in the area was determined as follows.

SUPERORDO: *LAMIANAE*

Ordo: *Scrophulariales*

Fam.: *Scrophulariaceae* Juss.

Genus: *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.)

1. *V. agrimoniifolium* (C. Koch.) Huber – Morath (*Celsia agrimoniifolium* C. Koch, *C. Heterohylla* Desf.)
2. *V. cheiranthifolium* Boiss.
3. *V. erivanicum* E. Wulf
4. *V. flavidum* (Boiss.) Freyn. & Bornm.
5. *V. formosum* Fisch. ex Schrank
6. *V. georgicum* Benth.
7. *V. gossypinum* Bieb.
8. *V. macrocarpum* Boiss.
9. *V. nudicaule* (Wydł.) Takht. [*Celsia nudicaule* (Wydł.) B. Fedtsch.]
10. *V. oreophilum* C. Koch
11. *V. orientale* (L.) All. (*Celsia orientalis* L.)
12. *V. paniculatum* E. Wulf
13. *V. phlomoides* L.
14. *V. phoeniceum* L.
15. *V. pyramidatum* Bieb.
16. *V. saccatum* C. Koch
17. *V. songaricum* Schrenk
18. *V. speciosum* Schrad.
19. *V. suworowianum* (C. Koch) O. Kuntze (*Celsia suworowianum* C. Koch) - Suvorov k.
20. *V. szovitsianum* Boiss.
21. *V. adenosepalum* (Murb.) Karjag.
22. *V. sinuatum* L.

Plant habitats on the Earth are very diverse. Geographical location of areas, groups of suitable species are their geographical elements. Geographical area types are an issue that is always in the attention of scientists, we often encounter questions such as how the geographical distribution of plants in different regions of Azerbaijan is grouped and what this is based on. The

general regularities of the distribution of the genus *Verbascum* L. in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic into geographical (areological) groups, their geographical elements were determined and analyzed based on the systems of N.N.Portenier [12, p. 26-33]. As a result of the conducted research, the following geographic-areal elements and areal types of the species included in the *Verbascum* L. genus were determined (Table 1). The study of geographical elements makes it possible to study the flora from a genetic or historical point of view, or rather, where and in what ways the species came to this area.

Based on the research results and literature sources, 11 geographic-areal elements of the species belonging to the *Verbascum* L. genus distributed in Nakhchivan AR have been determined: Eastern Mediterranean, Mediterranean Sea, Small Asia, Small Asia-Caucasus, Middle Asia, Iran-Central Asia, North Iran, North Iran-Caucasus, Iran-Turan, Atropatan, Central Europe. The following results were obtained during the analysis. 3 species of the *Verbascum* L. genus included in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic [*V. orientale* (L.) All. (*Celsia orientalis* L.), *Verbascum phoeniceum* L., *V. agrimoniifolium* (C. Koch.) Huber – Morath (*Celsia agrimoniifolium* C. Koch., *C. Heterophylla* Desf.)] it belongs to the Eastern Mediterranean geographical type.

A species [*Verbascum sinuatum* L.] is included in the Mediterranean geographic type. Two species [*Verbascum speciosum* Scchrad., *Verbascum flavidum* Boiss.] are included in the Minor Asia geographic type. A species [*Verbascum pyramidatum* Bieb.] included in the Asia Minor-Caucasian geographic type. A species [*Verbascum cheiranthifolium* Boiss.] is included in the Near Asian geographical type. A species [*Verbascum songoricum* Schrenk.] is included in Iran-Central Asian geographical type.

Five species [*Verbascum suworowianum* C. Koch., *Verbascum oreophilum* C. Koch., *Verbascum saccatum* C. Koch, *Verbascum adenosepalum* Murb., *Verbascum nuducaule* (Wyd.) Takht.] are included in the North Iran geographical type.

A species [*Verbascum gossypinum* Bieb.] is included in North Iran Caucasian geographical type. Two species [*Verbascum macrocarpum* Boiss., *Verbascum georgicum* Benth.] are included in Iran-Turanian geographic type.

Four species [*Verbascum formosum* Fisch. ex Schrank., *Verbascum paniculatum* E. Wulf., *Verbascum szovitsianum* Boiss., *Verbascum erivanicum* E. Wulf.] are included in Atropatan geographic type.

A species [*Verbascum phlomoides* L.] is included in Central European geographic type.

Table 1.

Percent indicator of geographic areal elements of the species included in the genus *Verbascum* L. in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic.

SN _o	Geographical areal elements	Name of species	% indicator
1.	Eastern Mediterranean	<i>V. orientale</i> (L.) All. (<i>Celsia orientalis</i> L.), <i>V. phoeniceum</i> L., <i>V. agrimoniifolium</i> (C. Koch.) Huber–Morath	13,6
2.	The Mediterranean Sea	<i>V. sinuatum</i> L.	4,55
3.	Minor Asia	<i>V. speciosum</i> Scchrad., <i>V. flavidum</i> (Boiss.) Freyn. & Bornm.	9,1
4.	Asia Minor-Caucasus	<i>V. pyramidatum</i> Bieb.	4,55
5.	Near Asia	<i>V. cheiranthifolium</i> Boiss.	4,55
6.	Iran-Central Asia	<i>V. songoricum</i> Schrenk	4,55
7.	Northern Iran	<i>V. suworowianum</i> (C. Koch), <i>V. oreophilum</i> C. Koch., <i>V. saccatum</i> C. Koch, <i>V. adenosepalum</i> (Murb.) Karjag., <i>V. nuducaule</i> (Wyd.) Takht.	22,7
8.	Northern Iran-Caucasus	<i>V. gossypinum</i> Bieb.	4,55
9.	Iran-Turan	<i>V. macrocarpum</i> Boiss., <i>V. georgicum</i> Benth.	9,1
10.	Atropathan	<i>V. formosum</i> Fisch. ex Schrank, <i>V. paniculatum</i> E. Wulf, <i>V. szovitsianum</i> Boiss., <i>V. erivanicum</i> E. Wulf	18,2
11.	Central Europe	<i>V. phlomoides</i> L.	4,55

As can be seen from the table, five of the species belonging to the genus *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.) distributed in the territory of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are included in the geographical element of North Iran, which is 22.7% of the total species. In addition, Atropatan geographical element with 18.2%, Eastern Mediterranean with 13.6%, Asia Minor and Iran-Turanian elements with 9.1%, Mediterranean, Asia Minor-Caucasus, Middle Asia, Iran-Central Asia, Northern Iran-Caucasus, Central European geographic elements are each represented by one species and make up 4.55% separately.

The complex ecological conditions belonging to the territory of the autonomous republic have a strong influence on the formation of vegetation, the growth and development of individual plant species, and the

emergence of various life forms. Considering this, it is important to study the characteristics of the species included in the genus (*Verbascum* L.) according to their life forms. The life form characterizes the degree to which plants adapt to the external environmental conditions that ensure metabolism.

Many systems of life forms are known (Hemistotermnoy, Kriofitnoy, Alpine, etc.). Prominent scientists O. Drude, J. Raunkier, J. Braun-Blanguet, I. G. Serebryakov and others created a large number of life form systems, taking into account one or another characteristic of plants. The analysis of the life forms of the species included in the genus *Verbascum* L. was carried out according to the classification of I.G.Serebryakov [13, p. 146-205; 17, p. 48-154].

Table 2.

Life forms of the species included in the *Verbascum* L. genus.

S№	Life forms	Number of species	Species % indicator
1.	Annual	<i>V. orientale</i> (L.) All. (<i>Celsia orientalis</i> L.)	4.5
2.	Biennial	<i>V. phoeniceum</i> L., <i>V. agrimoniifolium</i> (C. Koch.) Huber – Morath, <i>V. cheiranthifolium</i> Boiss., <i>V. speciosum</i> Schrad., <i>V. flavidum</i> (Boiss.) Freyn. & Bornm., <i>V. sinuatum</i> L., <i>V. suworowianum</i> (C. Koch) O. Kuntze, <i>V. saccatum</i> C. Koch, <i>V. adenosepalum</i> (Murb.) Karjag., <i>V. orientale</i> (L.) All. (<i>Celsia orientalis</i> L.), <i>V. paniculatum</i> E. Wulf, <i>V. szovitsianum</i> Boiss., <i>V. cheiranthifolium</i> Boiss., <i>V. macrocarpum</i> Boiss., <i>V. macrocarpum</i> Boiss., <i>V. gossypinum</i> Bieb., <i>V. phlomoides</i> L., <i>V. songaricum</i> Schrenk	81.8
3.	Perennial	<i>V. oreophilum</i> C. Koch, <i>V. nuducaule</i> (Wydł.) Takht., <i>V. pyramidatum</i> Bieb.	13.7

As can be seen from the table, biennial grasses with 18 species (81.8%) form the basis of the genus *Verbascum* L. in the area. In terms of the number of species, perennial grasses are in the second place with 3 species (13.7%), annual grasses are in the last place with one species (4.5%).

Result. Thus, as a result of the conducted scientific-research works, the species included in the genus *Verbascum* L. (*Celsia* L.) were studied in the territory of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic. The following results were obtained by studying the systematic composition and biomorphological characteristics of these plants.

During the research, a systematic analysis of the genus *Verbascum* L. was carried out in the flora of the Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic, and it was determined that 22 species of the genus are distributed in the area.

The species included in the genus *Verbascum* L. distributed in the flora of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic are represented in 11 geographical areal elements: [Eastern Mediterranean Sea (3 species), Mediterranean Sea (1 species), Asia Minor (2 species), Asia Minor-Caucasus (1 species), Middle Asia (1 species), Iran-Central Asia (1 species), Northern Iran (5 species), Northern Iran-Caucasus 1 species), Iran-Turanian (2 species), Atropatan (4 species), Central Europe (1 species)]. By carrying out an ecological analysis, the species distributed in the area are divided into 3 groups according to their life forms: a species is included annual species [*V. orientale* (L.) All. (*Celsia orientalis* L.)], 18 species are included biennials [*Verbascum phoeniceum* L., *V. agrimoniifolium* (C. Koch.) Huber – Morath (*Celsia agrimoniifolium* C. Koch, C. *Heterohylla* Desf.), *Verbascum sinuatum* L., *Verbascum flavidum* Boiss., *Verbascum speciosum* Schrad., *Verbascum cheiranthifolium* Boiss., *Verbascum songaricum* Schrenk., *Verbascum suworowianum* C. Koch., *Verbascum saccatum* C. Koch, *Verbascum adenosepalum* Murb., *Verbascum gossypinum* Bieb., *Verbascum macrocarpum* Boiss., *Verbascum georgicum* Benth., *Verbascum formosum* Fisch. ex Schrank., *Verbascum paniculatum* E. Wulf., *Verbascum szovitsianum* Boiss., *Verbascum erivanicum* E. Wulf., *Verbascum phlomoides* L.] and 3 species are included in perennials [*Verbascum pyramidatum* Bieb., *Verbascum oreophilum* C. Koch., *Verbascum nuducaule* (Wydł.) Takht.].

References

1. Əsgərov A.M. Azərbaycanın bitki aləmi (Ali bitkilər - Embryophyta). Bakı: TEAS Press Nəşriyyat evi, 2016, 443 s.
2. İbrahimov Ə.Ş., Talıbov T.H. Naxçıvan Muxtar Respublikasının təbii bitki ehtiyatları və onlardan səmərəli istifadə yolları // Azərb. Respb. Dövlət Elm və Texnika Komitəsi, Elm və Texnika Yenilikləri jurnalı, 2000, № 1 (4), s. 12-23
3. İbrahimov Ə.Ş., Talıbov T.H. Naxçıvan MR-in səhra biomüxtəlifliyi və onun nadir növlərinin mühafizəsi // Naxçıvan Regional Elm Mərkəzinin əsərləri, 2001, cild VI, bur.6, s.84
4. Qrossheym A.A. Azərbaycan florası. Bakı: Azərnəşr, Kənd təsərrüfatı şöbəsi, Cild 2, 1936, 543 s.
5. Nəbiyeva F.X. Naxçıvan Muxtar Respublikası ərazisində yayılmış Keçiqulağikimilər (Scrophulariaceae Juss.) fəsiləsi haqqında məlumat // AMEA Naxçıvan Bölməsinin Xəbərləri, 2016, № 2, s. 76-83.
6. Nəbiyeva F.X. Keçiqulağikimilər fəsiləsinin *Verbascum* cinsinə daxil olan növlərin tədqiqi // AMEA Naxçıvan Bölməsinin Elmi əsərləri, 2019, № 4, s. 73-79.
7. Novruzova E.S., Talıblı M.İ. Naxçıvan Muxtar Respublikası florasında yayılan Sığırquyuğu cinsinin öyrənilmə tarixi və əhəmiyyətli xüsusiyyətləri // Naxçıvan Dövlət Universiteti. "Elmi əsərləri". Təbiət və tibb elmləri seriyası. 2020, №3 (104), səh. 48-51
8. Talıbov T.H., İbrahimov Ə.Ş. Naxçıvan Muxtar Respublikası florasının taksonomik spektri. Naxçıvan: Əcəmi, 2008, 364 s.
9. Флора Азербайджана. Т. VII, 1957, 646 с.
10. Гроссгейм А.А. Флора Кавказа. Т. IV, М.-Л.: Изд-во АН СССР, 1950, с. 108-251.
11. Конспект флоры Кавказа. Ред. Г.Л. Кудряшова, И.В. Таганова, М.-СПб. Товарищество научных изданий КМК, 2012, т. 1-3(2), 623 с. (142 - 217)
12. Портениер Н.Н. Система географических элементов флоры Кавказа. Ботанический журнал, 2000, Москва, Т. 85, № 9, с. 26-33
13. Серебряков И.Г. Жизненные формы растений и их изучение // Полева геоботаника. М.: Наука, 1964, Т. 3, с. 146-205
14. APG III. 2009. An update of the Angiosperm Phylogeny Group classification for the orders and families of flowering plants. APG III. Botanical Journal of the Linnean Society 161: 105–121

15. Flora Irana. Flora des iranischen hochlandes und der umrahmenden qebirge. Von univ. Prof. Dr. Karl Heinz Rechinger. Erster Direktor des Naturhistorischen Museums in Wien (emertus). Akademische Druck-u Verlagsanstalt. Graz-Austria, 1967, 1968, 1981, 1984

16. Flora of Turkey and the East Aegean Islands, Vol. II by P. H. Davis. Edinburgh University Press, 1982, 948 p.

17. Raunkier C.R. The life form of plants and statistical plant geography, Clarendon Press. Oxford:1934, p. 48-15